

An example of a deep classifier for contour shapes inspired by the almost complete analytical descriptor known by the GCSS

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Abstract– The contours describing objects within an image are considered to be relevant and useful information in various fields such as classification. Although the description of the contours remains a problem to be solved, several shape descriptors have been proposed in the literature. Among this large set of approaches, we mention the family of multi-scale descriptors, more particularly the Curvature Scale Space (CSS) descriptor [8]. It is obtained by the extraction of the zero-crossing points of the smoothed contour with a succession of Gaussian kernels in different scales. CSS is robust to noise, scale and orientation changes of the objects. For this, it has been approved and adopted by the norm MPEG for shape similarity retrieval in large image datasets in 2000. However, CSS do not verify the almost completeness property defined as the pre-completion for a given resolution due to the need to deal with quantified data that implies never tending to the theoretical completeness. This property has been achieved thanks to the generalized version of CSS by Benkhelifa et al. [2]. The Generalized Curvature Scale Space (GCSS) is a set of finite and $E(2)$ invariant points considered as an enrichment of CSS descriptors. It focuses on the regions with high curvature variations while in CSS, the smoothed contour is only described by its extrema. GCSS features are also robust to noise and stable. They have been normalized latter [1] in order to enable the classification of the extracted points possible using Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and the Euclidean distance employed as a similarity metric instead of the Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) distance previously used for calculating the distance between GCSS descriptors of different classes. In this context, the task of the classification of 2D contours has been studied using various deep learning techniques. Some of them classified row contour data [3] and others performed this task given the generated description of contours as input ([7,4]. In both cases, CNNs were applied for

	Convolution with random kernels (R1, R2, R3, R4 and R5)					Convolution with predefined gaussian kernels g (with σ varies from 1 to 5)				
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FIGURE 1 – The difference between applying predefined kernels and the typical random ones used in CNN feature extraction blocks given as input a contour from MPEG-7 dataset (presented in black). On the left : the result the convolution with five kernels with random weights. On the right : the outputs of a CNN convolutional layers whose layers are set to be Gaussian kernel with σ varies from 1 to 5 with a step of 1.

extracting inexplicable features being used for the classification. These last are obtained because of the random initialization of the weights that are next updated through the evolution of the training process. However, it is possible to personalize the CNN layers in order to obtain a specific representation such as smoothed curves using Gaussian kernels. The difference between applying predefined kernels and random ones within the feature extraction block is illustrated in figure 1. To the best of our knowledge, there is no previous work unveiling the black box nature of CNNs and focusing on the hybridization of deep neural networks with analytical methods for the purpose of shape description. In this work, we merge DL approaches with statistical ones. Hence, we propose the very first deep learning robust and explainable model for the classification of 2D, closed and planar contours : DeepGCSS. The features extraction layers of the proposed model are a deep version of the Generalized Curvature Scale Space (GCSS) descriptors. The proposed architecture is detailed in figure 2 where the feature extraction block is composed of three types of layers : convolutional layers, customized layers for curvature computation and max-pooling layers. Within first type of layers, we define 1D convolutional layers whose kernels represent the first and second derivatives of gaussian kernels (respectively denoted by $g_u(u, \sigma_n)$ and $g_{uu}(u, \sigma_n)$) with multiple standard deviation values. This enables the customized layers to compute the invariant curvature features denoted by $k(u, \sigma_n)$ and computed as follow :

$$\kappa(u, \sigma_n) = \dot{x}(u, \sigma_n)\ddot{y}(u, \sigma_n) - \dot{y}(u, \sigma_n)\ddot{x}(u, \sigma_n) \quad (1)$$

Where $\dot{x}(u, \sigma)$ is the result of the convolution of the x coordinates of the contour with the first de-

FIGURE 2 – DeepGCSS generic architecture for 2D contour classification

Architecture	Parameters number			# Training Epochs	Validation Accuracy
	Features extraction block	Fully connected	Total		
AlexNet in case of contour images	554 048	37 793 802	38 347 850	400K	96%
ContourCNN	31 040	205 690	236 730	100K	96%
DeepGCSS	320 (non-trainable params)	114 310 (trainable params)	114 630	3K	95.15%

TABLE 1 – Comparative study : DeepGCSS vs other deep architectures

derivative of the Gaussian kernel $g_u(u, \sigma_n)$ at scale σ and $\ddot{x}(u, \sigma)$ is the result of the convolution of the x coordinates of the contour with the second derivative of the Gaussian kernel $g_{uu}(u, \sigma_n)$ at scale σ (respectively for $\dot{y}(u, \sigma)$ and $\ddot{y}(u, \sigma)$). These invariant features undergo a max-pooling operation since the regions having higher curvature values are feature vector that represents the shapes of object boundaries. Pooling the most active features is similar to the extraction of maximum curvature values in GCSS. DeepGCSS extracted features are represented in figure 3. These

FIGURE 3 – Features extracted within DeepGCSS architecture for a smoothed boundary of a given shape from MPEG-7 dataset with σ varies from 1 to 5. The radius of red circles presents the curvature value at each given point. The bigger the circle, the higher the curvature at the given point.

last are next concatenated and go through our implemented dropout layer. It shows which values of σ are mostly involved in shape recognition. At the end, we feed these last to the classification block. The only trainable weights in our model are those of the classification part which consists of a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) that is added to perform the classification and where the weights are trainable. Such architecture is firstly essential to establish a comparison between the efficiency of hand-crafted kernels and the learned ones and secondly to study the ability of the classifier to map the input data into an invariant representation. include MPEG-7 and MNIST contour datasets.

On the one hand, we compare DeepGCSS with other Deep learning models and summarize our experimental results giving MNIST contour dataset in table 1. DeepGCSS has the least number of parameters due to its feature extraction block. Thanks to the GCSS recall, this block contains only 320 non-trainable parameters. Therefore, our model is the most reduced in terms of parameter number. Our model converges faster than AlexNet in the case of contour images which take around 400k epochs and contourCNN which converges within around 100k. Even though the number of parameters in the DeepGCSS model is much smaller compared to the conventional contour classifiers, the performance remains close. The two approaches reach similar validation accuracy of around 96% whereas DeepGCSS accuracy is equal to 95.15%. It has been proved in [5][6][9] that a higher accuracy of a given contour classifier doesn't obligatory lead to a robust model. For instance, the robustness of DeepGCSS is equal to 80.4%. On the other hand, we compare invariants extracted by the DeepGCSS to a set of analytical methods of the state of the art giving MPEG-7 shapes dataset. Results are listed in table 2. We remark that DeepGCSS gives a competitive score compared to the presented set of methods. The accuracy and robustness of our deep model has been proven

Contour flexibility	89.31%
IDSC	85.40%
Is-match	84.97%
Skeletal context	79.92%
GCSS	78.84%
CPDH	76.56%
SC	76.51%
Visual parts	76.45%
CSS	75.44%
ASD	70.51%
DeepGCSS	68.57%
SSD	61.00%
Curve normalization	50.76%

TABLE 2 – Comparative study with statistical methods tested on MPEG7 dataset [2].

given MNIST dataset which contains a large number of samples. However, the obtained score using MPEG-7 (a relatively small dataset), is not that much high. But the model yet robust. The low accuracy is explained by the high intra-class variation and the presence of symmetrical objects. The use of GCSS-based contour descriptors brings two important benefits. First, GCSS-based features allow the DNN to map input data into an invariant and almost-complete representation. Second, GCSS hand-crafted features have explainable descriptiveness different from conventional CNN features whose theoretical understanding is still unclear. The proposed model naturally extracts areas with strong curvatures. These zones, robust to geometrical transformations and to noise, characterize the shape and subsequently accelerate the convergence and stability during learning.

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